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“WHEN LIFE GIVES YOU FLOWERS”

When life gives you flowers
Expect the thorns
Piercing pains that you have to endure
But these make you strong

When life gives you flowers
Expect the bees, drawn to your beauty
Bringing pollens of growth
And these make you productive

When life gives you flowers
Expect the worms, feeding on leaves
Criticisms that make or break
Yet, these make you humble

When life gives you flowers
Expect the butterflies
Beautiful and light moments
These make you smile

When life gives you flowers
Expect the parasitic pests
Gnawing your daily toils
But these make you resilient

When life gives you flowers
Expect the dew in the morning
Sparkling and invigorating
This refreshes your weary soul

When life gives you flowers
Embrace them, be grateful

For flowers come in colors and kinds
Today is a bouquet, tomorrow could be a garden

